
Evaluation And Assessment of Water Resources in Ghana Towards Meeting Future Demands

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Abstract

Ghana as a country is blessed with all the natural sources of water; rainwater, water from water bodies, spring water and ground water. This has served the Ghanaian economy for centuries and has met demands of all kinds and still meeting demands. But current illegalities such as illegal gold mining activities, bad waste disposal, bad drainage works is destroying water bodies and water resources and hence a fall in demand especially in the direction of surface water. This has resulted in most gold mining communities depending on ground water to meet daily needs. This research work hence sorts to investigate the current nature of water resources in Ghana and its ability to meet future demands in serving generations to come. Research findings establishes that avoidance of buffer zone protection policy by illegal gold miners has led to mining on water bodies and destruction of natural river channels. The future of surface water bodies in meeting demand is under threat as total destruction of surface water bodies will result in a break in hydrological cycle. Bad hydraulic structures and reduction in drain size is resulting in decrease in runoff generation from impervious areas to contribute to river water volume and amount. Government agencies and all stakeholders needs to help work on water bodies in Ghana to bring to a state which will be aesthetically nice for recreational purposes whiles meeting daily water demands. Indigenous also have to avoid sole dependence on groundwater and rainwater in meeting demands. And make use of water from water bodies like Birim, Supong, Pra, Densu etc as an addition in order to save the resource for now and future generations.

Keywords: Hydrological cycle, water cycle, climate change, resources, demands, assessment, evaluation,

1 INTRODUCTION

Water bodies in Ghana has served generation and will continue to serve generation. But there is a fall in quality and deterioration to a greater extent due to illegal activities on water bodies hence a threat on water resources in meeting future demands. Ghana has a lot of water bodies such as Birim, Densu, Ankobra, Antoa, Akusu, Supong, Pra, White and Black Volta, Oti, Bosomtwe, Tano etc. and these water bodies has served the Ghanaian economy over several decades and still in the position to do more. In the 1990's, water sources obtained from these water bodies were in its finest form of high quality in meeting household demands, for power generation and for other purposes. This is not the case in the 2020's as illegal gold mining activities on these water bodies has damaged the quality and aesthetics nature of such water bodies. Because all these water bodies are being destroyed through illegal gold mining activities, the continuous and cyclic nature of the hydrological cycle is being destroyed gradually. Water bodies and natural channels of water bodies are being destroyed as illegal gold mining activities are happening on the water bodies and being turned into lands after destruction of these natural river channels. The flow of water in rivers and streams is always from upstream to downstream and ends up joining other water bodies or the sea. The illegal gold mining and other illegal activities on the water bodies is destroying this natural course resulting in threats to water bodies and its future in Ghana. Illegal gold mining activities has been in existence for several years but its severity since 2010 due to man's greediness and

quest for riches is destroying the water bodies at a faster rate hence the resultant threats to the future of water bodies in Ghana. Protection of water bodies and its sustenance is very important for the now and future generations. I believe the uncaring nature of Ghanaians and even the international world towards some water bodies has resulted in their extinction from the earth surface. With this in mind, it's very important to assess water bodies, analyze their existence and what is resulted in their existence from generation to the now generation and what can be done to protect it for the future. There is a saying that 'little drops of water makes a mighty ocean' and so is the source of most river and water bodies in Ghana. Most of them are coming as spring water from rocks and sprouting as drops but ends up as pool of water downstream and becoming assessable to mankind to meet demands of all kinds. Ghana as a country is blessed with two rainy season in southern part and one rainy season in the northern part. This two rainy season in the eastern part of Ghana is helping and contribution into the hydrological cycle in to a higher extent. This is not the case in the northern part as it's not much forested and vegetation cover is low with fewer water bodies hence contribution into the hydrological cycle being low. Most of their sources of water in communities are from dugouts and dams constructed at vantage points to collect rainwater during peak periods. The White Volta with its source from Burkina is serving most communities during mean periods of rainfall to meet demands of crop production and human consumption through activities such as irrigation. The correlation and relationship that exist between ground water,

surface water and rain water is perfect and intertwined as each contributes into the other. Rainwater contributes to streams and rivers through direct rainfall and runoff generation during precipitations. This same rainwater contributes to underground water through infiltration and seepage into the soil and movement into aquifers for storage and future abstraction. Most of these aquifers are channeled into streams with some quashing out of rocks as spring water or drops of water. Such drops of water comes out sequentially and ends up as pool of water downstream flowing through natural channels. Such downstream flow of water gets evaporated during sunny days into the sky to go through processes to form clouds for further precipitation on lands hence cyclical. Evapotranspiration from plants also contributes into this cycle after abstraction by plants roots. This is what is called the hydrological cycle. With this cycle in defined circumstances, surface water bodies are sustained, revived and maintained to serve salient purposes in Ghana. There is hence the need to monitor and use wisely all the resources such as forest reserves, forest, rocks which mostly serve as aquifers and lands helping in the creation of natural channels. By protecting and using such resources wisely water bodies will be protected to serve the future generations.

1. REVIEW OF RELATED WORKS ON WATER RESOURCES ASSESSMENT, HYDROLOGICAL CYCLE AND IMPACTS

1.1 Water Resources in Ghana

In Ghana as at 2014, the renewable freshwater resources per capita were pegged at 1131 (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018). Basically, the freshwater resources in Ghana comprise surface water

include Volta river system, South-Western and Coastal River Systems (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018). The Red, Black and White Volta Rivers as well as the Oti River comprise of the Volta river systems. The Bia, Tano, Ankobra and Pra rivers constitute the South-Western river systems. The Tordzie/Aka, Densu, Ayensu, Ochi-Nakwa and Ochi-Amisah form the Coastal river systems (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018). These river systems make up 70%, 22% and 8%, respectively of the total land area of about 240,000km². In addition, the sole natural freshwater lake in Ghana is Lake Bosumtwi (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018). This is a meteoritic crater lake located in the forest zone, with a surface area of 50km² and a maximum depth of 78m (MWRWH - Ghana National Water Policy, 2007; WRC Ghana, 2012). In Ghana, though much has been done on water resources, documentaries, news items and more significantly literature on water resources are more disjointed and not strongly incorporated in policy documents, strategic action plans and reports produced by non-governmental organizations (NGOs), consultants and international entities (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018). The quality of groundwater and surface water resources keeps worsening mainly due to soaring levels of pollution from “galamsey” (illegal gold mining), waste from drains during runoff, leachate from chemical fertilizers and pesticides used in agriculture, chemicals from mining, and use of chemicals in fishing coupled with rapid population growth has entirely left Ghana’s water resources ungovernable (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018). The existing water management strategies employed is not robust enough to cover the challenges. Man’s quest for riches and beauty has made man so eager in search of rich gold in

Ghana hence the overexploitation of land and water resources in Ghana. This has led to the destruction of the quality and quantity of most water bodies such as river Birim in the Eastern Region of Ghana. Management, protection and maintenance practices by government agencies in Ghana such as Ministry of Water Resources, Works and Housing, Water Resources commission is not stringent enough to enforce the laws binding water resources, demands and usage. Over the past 6 years and counting, Ghana's per capita availability of water resources is reducing daily. The effect of climate change leading to variability in precipitation is one of the challenges our country faces at present, which often result in floods as we recorded in the June 3rd twin disaster in Accra, Ghana in 2014 (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018).

2.2 Water resources demands in Ghana

Water as finite good is in demand to a greater extent in every country in meeting all kinds of daily demands. Ghana as a country is no exception as demands of water for cooking, washing, fishing, irrigation, watering of lawns, hydropower generation, farming etc are met on daily basis towards the development and growth of the country. This met at a higher rate annually due to the availability of all the types of water sources in Ghana; rainwater, surface water and groundwater. Rainwater harvesting in the homes is the means by which rainwater is made available to meet demands. Surface water from water bodies such as Densu, Akobra, Birim, Pra, Supong etc are made available for usage in the homes either by direct fetching or abstraction to treatment organizations such as

Ghana Water Company Limited for treatment, storage and distribution to homes through distribution networks. Ghana's groundwater resources are made up of three geological formations with 54%, 45% and 1% for the basement complex (metamorphic rocks and crystalline igneous), the consolidated sedimentary formations, and the Cenozoic and Mesozoic sedimentary rocks, respectively (Ghana National Water Policy 2007). Occurrence of groundwater in the basement complex is linked to the development of secondary porosity hence causing the fracturing, jointing, shearing and weathering. Aquifers depth normally ranged from 10 to 60 m with yields hardly exceeding 6 metres cubic per hour (MWRWH - Ghana National Water Policy 2007; WRC Ghana 2012). The Cenozoic and Mesozoic formations that usually occur in the extreme South Eastern and Western part of Ghana are also limestone aquifers with depth range of 120m to 300m (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018). Reservoirs or dams for impoundments have been created for the purpose of water supply, irrigation, hydroelectric power generation and ecosystem support (Yeleeiere et. al., 2018). Mostly in the northern region of Ghana, is the dams and dugouts for the impoundment of water during the rainy season for storage towards meeting water demands during the dry season. This is used to meet demands such as for irrigation, demands in the homes such as for cooking, bathing, drinking, cooking, feeding animals, construction of roads etc.

2.3 Impacts of climate changes on water resources

Variability in activities on the surface of the earth will result in climate changes and the resultant effect on water resources

and land. Water resources are in fact arguably the most important domain to be considered in a climate change impact assessment study. This importance stems from the fact that climate change has direct impacts on the availability, timing and variability of the water supply and demand, and is also related to the significant consequences of these impacts on many sectors of our society (Cunha et al., 2007). Water is used for human consumption, industrial purposes, irrigation, power production, navigation, recreation and waste disposal, as well as for the maintenance of healthy aquatic ecosystems. Its availability and the occurrence of extreme events, such as floods and droughts, condition the location of urban, industrial and agriculture areas, power generation plants and trading centres (Cunha et al., 2007). The intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC) Third Assessment Report (IPCC, 2001) estimates a global increase of mean annual temperature of 0.8°C to 2.6°C by 2050, and 1.4°C to 5.8°C by 2100. The study also reports results that indicate an increase in annual precipitation induced by climate change in high and mid latitudes and most equatorial regions, as well as a general decrease in the subtropics. Results also show that flood magnitude and frequency is likely to increase, due to the concentration of precipitation in winter in most areas of the globe. (Cunha et al., 2007). As regards the impacts of climate change in Europe, the IPCC studies suggest that Southern Europe, and the Mediterranean region, will be particularly affected in a negative way. This will be especially true in the Iberian Peninsula, south of the River Tagus, where a considerable increase in temperature and a reduction in

precipitation and runoff are expected by 2100 (Cunha et al., 2007). The current global climate models (GCMs) and regional climate models (RCMs) are able to produce time series for a set of climatic variables under different emission scenarios. The basic scenario, commonly referred to as the control run, consists of simulating the conditions in the absence of any CO₂ increase, thus producing a stationary climatic scenario, where each climatic variable varies throughout the simulation periods but its overall average is not expected to change (Cunha et al., 2007). This variability in the climate expected to result in different rainfall regimes and the resultant effect on surface water and ground water. Ground water recharge is always from surface water and the current illegalities and destruction of water bodies through illegal gold mining activities is likely to affect this cause in the future. The duration of dry season in the southern part of Ghana is not long as compared to the northern part of Ghana. Hence in comparison, lands in the northern part are much degraded as compared to the southern part. The southern part has rich lands because of the two rainfall season experienced each year. This two rainfall regimes replenishes and maintains the water bodies for its existence and survival. This is what has sustained the water bodies over the years but current illegal gold mining activities, pollution, contamination, destruction of natural water body channels and runoff generation full of debris into water bodies is likely to result in the extinction of the water bodies in the future. The pressure on groundwater resources has increased over the years due to the destruction of surface water bodies hence resulting to the use of water from boreholes and wells to meet water demands.

2.4 The hydrological cycle and impacts on water resources

The earth's hydrological cycle links interactions between the atmosphere, lithosphere, biosphere and anthroposphere, and it is also profoundly affected by human activities and socio-economic development (Dawen et al., 2021). With recent rapid changes in climate and land use, the global hydrological cycle is experiencing high levels of spatial and temporal variability, which has resulted in numerous water-related issues that pose challenges to human water security. Therefore, obtaining a better understanding of the hydrological cycle and water resources has become a key concern for environmental and natural resources research (Braga et al., 2014; Xia et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2010a). Water resources are renewable due to its cyclical nature of the hydrological cycle. However, variability in climate and land surfaces means that the hydrological cycle and water resources are highly heterogeneous in both space and time. Presently, more than four billion people are affected by water shortages (Mekonnen and Hoekstra, 2016). The development and use of water resources have already surpassed the alarm level in many parts of the world, including China, thereby resulting in environmental issues including: rivers with little or no flow (Liang et al., 2010); ecosystem degradation (Palmer and Ruhj, 2019); water table decline (Bierkens and Wada, 2019); and lake/wetland shrinking (Zhou et al., 2019). Literature review indicates the current status and existing issues of hydrological cycle and water resource research in the context of global climate change. It discusses the major challenges, key scientific issues and potential future

research directions that need to be addressed in the future (Dawen et al., 2021).

2.5 Hydrological cycle under global change

In assessment and discussion on global warming, changes in the atmospheric system have accelerated temporal and spatial changes in the hydrological cycle (Milly et al., 2005; Taylor et al., 2013), as well as exacerbating global and regional water shortages (Schewe et al., 2014). Climate change characterized by rising temperatures and more frequent extreme events such as heat waves, heavy rains, floods, sudden droughts and persistent droughts have become critical concerns for the scientific community, governments, and the public (IPCC, 2014; Hao et al., 2018). This is because of return period's possibility within the global world resulting from climate change which will result in a one-time disaster. Hence a concern which needs to be addressed through forecasting, management and control. Under climate warming, the global terrestrial cryosphere has undergone changes involving glacier retreat, snow reduction and permafrost degradation, all of which affects the hydrological cycle (Ding et al., 2020). These impacts are in addition to those created by human activities (Vörösmarty et al., 2000; Wang et al., 2010b). Humans affect the hydrological cycle through greenhouse gas emissions (Gordon et al., 2005; Piao et al., 2007; IPCC, 2014), as well as through water conservation projects and water consumption activities (Haddeland et al., 2014; Tang et al., 2015; Wada et al., 2017). Rapid population growth and increased consumption levels have put unprecedented pressure on the world's water

resources (Dosdogru et al., 2020). Demands for water to meet daily demands such as for drinking, irrigation, hydropower generation and address food insecurity hence is a problem due to population growth and increased migration. Numerous studies are now focusing on the impacts of these global change on water resources (Tang, 2020). The use of long-term historical data to analyze changes in the frequency, duration and intensity of hydrometeorological extreme events is the basis for understanding the impacts of climate change on hydrology (Dawen et al., 2021). Sufficient evidence exists to indicate that climate change has already led to significant changes in the water cycle (Gudmundsson et al., 2021). In recent decades, attribution analysis of extreme events has developed rapidly, where long-term observations and model simulations, such as the CMIP climate model (Yang et al., 2020), have been used to compare the probability of extreme events in the presence or absence of climate change. Naveau et al. (2020) have developed methods for fractional attribution risk framework and optimal fingerprinting.

3 AVAILABLE WATER RESOURCES ASSESSED FOR ANALYSIS

It deem fit to evaluate and assess all the available surface water bodies available in Ghana to establish its quality, quantity, availability and its ability in meeting current demands before forecasting for meeting future demands. Various water bodies and water resources within towns and villages in Ghana were assessed to establish the quality, availability and usage in meeting demands. Water bodies assessed includes White Volta (WV), River Birim, River Spong, River Akusu, Asumoia, and

Densu. The water quality, quantity and importance in Ghana is deteriorating at a faster rate due illegal gold mining within some communities in Ghana. Water as an economic good is serving all the Ghanaian population in meeting water demand in diverse ways. Some of the demands met include for drinking, cooking, washing, watering of lawns, hydropergeneration, for irrigation during dry season farming, feeding animals etc. The surface water bodies in Ghana is under a serious threat due to the inception and acceptance of illegal gold mining in Ghana. The water is being polluted to a higher degree by these illegal gold miners as they make us of and release harmful chemicals such as cyanide into the water bodies during the gold extraction process. Some illegal gold miners contaminate and pollute the water during the washing process in order to obtain the gold. Some even dig the soil and release them into the water body and by that destroying the natural channel of the water body. All water bodies are connected in nature as water from the upstream of a river will end up joining another water body. The destruction of water bodies in Ghana especially in the southern part has been from ages but rampant now due to the surge in illegal gold mining business in Ghana. The desire for riches and quest for more money is making the youth venture into gold mining as is one of the easiest ways of getting employment in Ghana.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 The water cycle and future impacts on water resources

The hydrological cycle also known as the water cycle needs a balance at all times in order to have water in the sky (rain water), surface water and ground water for continuity. The interconnection and relationship that exist between rain water, surface water and ground water is what is resulting in the sustenance of the cycle. Areas in Ghana with maximum rainfall and two seasonal rainfall have a lot water bodies contributing into the hydrological cycle both above land and underground. Underground water gushing out as spring water and rain water are the main sources of surface water or water bodies in Ghana. And these two sources are part of the hydrological cycle hence the main contributor of water and impacting on water resources to a higher degree. Any break in the trend or cycle results on a negative impact on the other. Surface water resources or water bodies have seen a major boost in the amount and quantity of water within a natural channel from upstream to downstream because of constant feeding and recharge from rainwater and ground water. Hence the water cycle impacting the water resources positively in Ghana. But illegal gold mining activities is resulting in all negative repercussions which in the future will impact on water bodies and resources negatively. Destruction of lands for gold mining and mining on water bodies is gradually damaging the hydrological cycle infinitesimally which will in the near future result in greater impact or a break in the hydrological cycle. Illegal gold miners are destroying lands which is the mother

source for all infiltration activities after storms. The dug soils also ends up in water bodies when moved by excavators. Mining on water bodies also have soil dug and left on the water body and ends up destroying the natural channel of the water body. Field investigations proved that when such areas are left unattended to, it ends up turning into water log areas and finally becoming lands during the dry season. Since the illegal gold mining is rampant, continues destruction of these natural water channels and creation of new ones (without proper engineering works) and water bodies may end up killing all the surface water bodies. When this happens there will be no connection between surface water and ground water. Surface water bodies does recharges groundwater and vice versa resulting in confined and unconfined aquifer recharges towards storage and upstream abstraction for future use. Disconnection between the two will impact land resources negatively. Plant growth will be a problem and resultant evapotranspiration from plants and evaporation from water bodies into the sky for rainfall formation and falling unto the land. When there is no precipitation, surface water bodies' replenishment will be a problem. Soil moisture and humid lands to support plant growth will be another problem resulting in land degradation as lands are infertile, dry and not loamy in nature to support food production. These will lead to food insecurity on the Ghanaian economy as can be seen in the northern part of Ghana as most farming activities occur during the rainy season with little dry season farming in the dry season. Food production and feeding of the Ghanaian economy is in a good position as rich lands in the southern part is supporting this

cause. But current illegalities in gold mining activities and destruction of lands, forest reserves and water bodies may lead to the break or destruction of the water cycle (hydrological cycle) and the resultant future consequences or repercussions as discussed above.

4.2 States of hydraulic structures and impacts on runoff generation

Runoff generation and collection into a hydraulic structure to be moved downstream and into a river or stream is one of the main ways in which surface water bodies are recharged. Ghana a developing country is facing challenges when it comes to infrastructure and economic development. Almost all the towns in Ghana have drainage systems to move runoffs from upstream of drains to downstream and finally ending in water bodies. But they are not in good shapes, not of adequate capacity or filled with soil, weeds or debris and hence decreasing the drain capacity and its ability to collect a lot of runoffs. With this mind, overland flows and runoff generation is mostly high resulting in most of the runoffs infiltrating into the soil instead of being turned into runoffs to end in water bodies to increase the amount of water. Drain capacity and subsequent runoff collection is dependent on runoff area and time concentration. Runoffs volume and depth is always high impervious areas and low within pervious areas. The pervious surface areas are very large and vegetative in nature having all kinds of plants and crops hence contributing to high rate of infiltration and humidifying of soil during precipitation. The impervious areas are small and mostly found within the centre

of the cities, towns and villages generation runoffs of varied volumes during precipitation. These generated and collected runoffs from the impervious areas then enter the drains and finally into water bodies to increase its volume and amount. Most of the drains are U – shaped with no covering hence exposed to all kinds of waste and soil. By this it is easy to reduce the drain capacity all the time once there is waste materials, soil debris etc. Most of the big hydraulic structures or drains are found in the cities where most of the areas are impervious and a high rate of runoff collection is of great importance to avoid flooding. It is therefore necessary to work on all these hydraulic and drainage structures, design and construct having adequate and standardized capacity in order to carry all runoffs and meet future runoffs due to urbanization and development. Once this is done, drains of adequate capacities will be obtained to help in runoff generations to increase water volumes and quantity. This will help the survival and maintaining of water bodies and resources in Ghana to meet future demands. With population growth likely to increase yearly, immigration is likely to surge as people travel for greener pastures, as man's water needs get increased yearly and with various water demands to be met. Because of climate changes and the need for increase in water volume within water bodies, international standardized hydraulic structures needs to be constructed to meet future runoff generation demands and final disposals to increase water bodies' volume.

4.3 illegal gold mining and buffer zone protection policy

Buffer zone protection policy has been in existence over the years as given by water resources commission to protect water bodies. With this protection policy, farmers and citizens are not allowed to farm or work 5m away from any surface water body or water resources. This helped protect the water body to a greater extent as farmers obeys and practice this policy. But current illegalities in activities such as gold mining can see gold miners digging and exploring lands resources very close (1m) to water bodies. This has posed threat to water bodies as river Birim, river Supong, Akusu etc have been destroyed by exploring buffer zones lands and mining on water bodies. This has destroyed the water bodies and contamination to a higher degree as water within these rivers are turbid, full of soil, low in oxygen to support fishing. It is therefore very important for these illegal gold miners to make use of standard operating procedures whenever when they want to explore and extract gold. Government agencies also need to step up their game in combating the illegal gold mining canker in Ghana. Other agencies such as private bodies and NGO's also needs to join the government of Ghana in fighting illegal gold mining activities in order to protect water bodies and water resources for now and the future. The future of surface water bodies in Ghana is bleak and requires stringent action and behaviour from all able bodies to help fight illegal gold mining activities, manage and protect the surface water bodies for the future. Buffer zone protection policy is protecting water bodies and leaving them in a clean and healthy state to meet demands. But

illegal gold mining has abrogated this policy and need to be stringent in order to protect water bodies from infringements and contamination.

4.4 Surface water resources and attitude by users

In analyzing the use of water in the 1990s within the study areas, the main sources of water was from surface water and ground water. The use of water from River Akusu, River Supong, River Birim etc. was to meet daily demands like cooking, washing, drinking, bathing, watering etc. Harvesting of rain water was used to buttress this purpose on daily basis. Surface water by then time was seen as a useful resource and economic good to meet daily demands and hence treated with care even though there was illegal gold mining in some of the towns. This is not the case in 2023 during this research as compared to years back. Surface water is currently under threat of destruction and possibility of extinction if care is not take to help curb the illegal gold mining canker. People attitude towards the economic good is very bad and no one seems to care about the natural resources. Because of this, there is no human use of the resource to meet demands such as drinking, washing, cooking, watering, irrigation etc. The main use of the water bodies within the study area is for illegal gold mining and washing of cars. In years back, this economic good was used for spraying of cocoa farms together with chemicals but no more used for irrigation because of its turbid nature and high level of contamination. Indigenous attitudes towards the resources is very bad as it cannot be used to support bathing but those who try to bath with it does that in the water. The chiefs, water user

association and lovers of water got to help to protect the water body for now and the future. Due to the high rate and demand for easy sources of water, ground water abstraction and borehole installations is on the rise. This is an attitude which needs to be avoided and look at surface water bodies again with good attitude and behaviour. By that groundwater can be assessed and used together with surface water and rainwater in meeting demands and serving future generations.

4.5 Potential of water resources to meet future demands

Illegal gold mining activities and poor state of the accessed water bodies like River Birim, River Akusu and River Supong poses threat to the water resources in meeting future demands. The demand for water in the future will surge due to migration, economic development and activities, and the need for water related development activities. It therefore deem fit to look and work on the current states of water bodies in the study area and in Ghana. This will make it attractive like can be seen in other developed countries like Dubai, USA, Canada, Germany, UK etc. and aesthetically also beautify the environment. The potential of current surface water resources in the study area and in Ghana being able to meet future demand needs further assessment, studies and analysis. This should be done together with rainwater and underground water for better understanding of the hydrological cycle of water movement in Ghana. This should be done in order to avoid future contingencies and meet future demands. People's quest for new things and illegal gold mining activities is really propagating the bad use of the water bodies such as river Birim

and polluting it respectively. The nature of water bodies such as River Birim, River Akusu, River Pra, River Supong etc is very bad and deteriorating at a high rate hence requiring stringent action and saving hand to save the economic good for now and the future.

5 CONCLUSION

Water as an economic good has served generation and will continue to serve future generation as it continues to exist within an area, a community or a country. Ghana as a country is blessed with a lot of surface water bodies which has served generation and still serving. But current illegalities in activities such as illegal gold mining, bad drainage system, bad disposal of waste, oil spillages etc is destroying almost all these natural resources. Current state of water bodies such as River Pra, River Birim, River Akusu, River Supong etc is very bad and deteriorating at faster rate. The water is very turbid, highly polluted and contaminated and unable to meet any demand in Ghana. Most of these water bodies have their outlet ending in another stream or river to continue pollution and contamination. With this reasons and others, it is likely these water bodies may extinct in the near future if no stringent action is taken to protect and nature the natural resource. This is because the hydrological has surface water as one its component to make the cycle complete. Therefore if one of the components exit from the others, the cycle may break and this may further lead to groundwater extinction as there is no source to recharge it. It is very important for government, agencies, private bodies, NGO's and all other stakeholders to

help work on these water bodies, nature, protect and beautify it for now and future generation. In Ghana only let alone other countries, the northern part have only one rainfall that is June July rainfall. The northern part of Ghana therefore have challenges with water during the dry season and the southern part needs to be careful not to fall into the same pit because a one or no rainfall regime in the southern part will be a problem in Ghana.

Acknowledgment

I am grateful to the Almighty God for the wisdom and strength granted unto me to complete this research work. Grateful I am to the study areas where I got the opportunity to access all water bodies for this research work.

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